

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SYNTAX AND SEMANTICS IN LANGUAGE

Yusupova Maftuna

2 nd year bachelor KSU named after Berdakh
Teaching foreign languages: English Philology.

Abdullayeva Sayyora Po'latovna

Supervisor.

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Abstract. Every language has rules that divide words into sentences and make communication clear and understandable. This article examines how these rules work, focusing on word order, sentence structure, and how the different parts of a sentence connect. It also studies how humans learn and process these rules, as well as their role in language technology such as translation and speech recognition. Understanding sentence structure helps improve language learning and linguistic research. This study highlights why these rules are important for humans to communicate effectively.

Keywords: Syntax, structure, sentence, meaning, semantic, semantic types.

СВЯЗЬ МЕЖДУ СИНТАКСИСОМ И СЕМАНТИКОЙ В ЯЗЫКЕ

Аннотация. В каждом языке есть правила, которые делят слова на предложения и делают общение ясным и понятным. В этой статье рассматривается, как работают эти правила, уделяя особое внимание порядку слов, структуре предложения и тому, как соединяются различные части предложения. В ней также изучается, как люди изучают и обрабатывают эти правила, а также их роль в языковых технологиях, таких как перевод и распознавание речи. Понимание структуры предложения помогает улучшить изучение языка и лингвистические исследования. В этом исследовании подчеркивается, почему эти правила важны для эффективного общения людей.

Ключевые слова: синтаксис, структура, предложение, значение, семантический, семантические типы.

Introduction

Syntax and Semantics are two fundamental components of language, each contributing to the formation and understanding of meaning in communication.

Syntax deals with how sentences are constructed, and users of human languages employ a striking variety of possible arrangements of the elements in sentences.

One of the most obvious yet important ways in which languages differ is the order of the main elements in a sentence. In English, for example, the subject comes before the verb and the direct object follows the verb, forming a standard Subject-Verb-Object (SVO) structure.(1)

On the other hand, Semantics deals with the literal meaning of words and the meaning of the way they are combined, which taken together form the core of meaning, or the starting point from which the whole meaning of a particular utterance is constructed. It is through the interaction of words and their meanings, along with their syntactic arrangement, that language users are able to derive the intended message.(3)

The relationship between syntax and semantics is of great importance in language comprehension and production. Syntax organizes the elements of a sentence, while semantics ensures that the elements convey meaningful information. This article examines the ways in which syntax and semantics interact, emphasizing their respective roles in sentence construction and meaning formation.

What's syntax

Syntax is the order of the words in a sentence. The term can be applied to how clauses, phrases, and qualifiers are ordered.

Types of Syntax:

Simple sentences

Complex sentences

Compound sentences

Compound -Complex sentences

1.Simple sentence

Sometimes it's best to keep it simple.

A simple syntactic structure is just a single independent clause.

Take this sentence for example:

"Tom went home." It's a full thought with a subject and verb. But a simple sentence doesn't always look so simple. "Tom, Harry, and Jean all decided to walk over to Tom's massive house" is a much longer sentence, but still a single independent clause.

2.Complex sentence

A complex sentence makes use of that dependent clause we were talking about. It combines dependent clauses with an independent clause.

Here's an example. "Since Bob was shy, he went to the prom alone." "Since Bob was shy" is dependent, and "he went to the prom alone" is independent- it could be its own sentence.

3. Compound sentence

A compound sentence contains two independent clauses, joined with a conjunction or a semicolon.

An example: "Kathy felt sick all day, but she continued to work on her physics project."

There are two clauses here which could be their own sentences: "Kathy felt sick all day" and "She continued to work on her physics project." They're put together with the conjunction "but."

4. Compound -Complex sentences

Compound AND complex? In this economy? That's right folks. A sentence can have multiple independent clauses and a dependent clause, making it compound-complex.

An example of such a monstrosity: "After they failed their project, Daniel wept for forgiveness and Kyle denounced Ms. Klempt as a tyrant." Can you spot which clause is which? "After they failed their project" is dependent, while "Daniel wept for forgiveness" and "Kyle denounced Ms. Klempt as a tyrant" are independent. (5)

Syntactic Rules

Syntax refers to the basic building blocks of how we communicate as human beings. While people can express themselves with language however they see fit, there are rarely broken.

1. All sentences require a subject and a verb. However, imperative sentences (commands) do not need to include their subject because it's assumed to be the person the sentence is directed at. nk." Not quite. "Wine Johnny drank." You get the point.

2. A single sentence should include one main idea. If a sentence includes two or more ideas, it's best to break it up into multiple sentences.

3. The subject comes first, and the verb comes second. If the sentence has objects, they come third, after the verb

4. Subordinate clauses (dependent clauses) also require a subject and verb. Below we explain more about how to use subordinate clauses in sentence structure

5. Adjectives and adverbs go in front of the words they describe. If there are multiple adjectives describing the same noun, use the proper adjective order, known as the "Royal Order.

Before we get into sentence structures, let's discuss syntactic patterns. In English, syntactic patterns are the acceptable word orders within sentences and clauses. Depending on what kinds of

words you want to use, such as indirect objects or prepositional phrases, there is a specific order in which to place them all. We've already talked about subjects and verbs, as well as direct objects and indirect objects, on our blog, but before we get to the syntactic patterns, we first need to explain complements and adverbials. Complements are words or phrases that describe other words in a sentence or clause. The difference between complements and other modifiers is that complements are necessary for the meaning of a sentence and cannot be removed.

There are three types of complements: subject complements, object complements, and adverbial complements. Subject complements describe the subject (That test was hard.), object complements describe the object (That test made me angry.), and adverbial complements describe the verb (That test took longer than usual.)(2)

Adverbials aren't always complements, however. While adverbial complements are necessary for a sentence's meaning, another kind of adverbial, modifier adverbials, can be removed without changing the meaning. Adverbials are usually composed of single adverbs (We ran quickly.), prepositional phrases (We ran in the park.), or noun phrases that relate to time (We ran this morning.)(2)

Be careful not to confuse adverbials with adverbial clauses, which are more involved and include their own subjects and verbs.

Subject → verb

The dog barked. This is the standard syntactic pattern, including the minimum requirements of just a subject and verb. The subject always comes first.

Subject → verb → direct object

The dog carried the ball. If the verb is transitive and uses a direct object, the direct object always goes after the verb

Subject → verb → subject complement

The dog is playful. The subject complement comes after the verb. Subject complements always use linking verbs, like be or seem.

Subject → verb → adverbial complement

The dog ate hungrily.

Like subject complements, adverbial complements come after the verb (if there are no objects). Be careful, because single adverbs can sometimes come before the verb; however, these are not complements. If you're not sure whether an adverb is a complement or not, try removing

it from the sentence to see if the meaning changes. If you find that removing it does change the meaning, it's an adverbial complement.(3)

Subject → verb → indirect object → direct object

The dog gave me the ball. Some sentences have both a direct object and an indirect object. In this case, the indirect object comes right after the verb, and the direct object comes after the indirect object. Keep in mind that objects of prepositions do not follow this pattern; for example, you can say, The dog gave the ball to me.

Subject → verb → direct object → object complement

The dog made the ball dirty. Object complements come after the direct object, similar to other complements.

Subject → verb → direct object → adverbial complement

The dog perked its ears up. When the sentence uses both a direct object and an adverbial complement, the direct object comes first, followed by the adverbial complement. In this syntax example, up is the adverbial complement because it describes how the dog perked its ears.(2)

Definition of Semantics

Semantics is the study of meaning in language. It can be applied to entire texts or to single words. In linguistics, semantics is the subfield that studies meaning. Semantics can address meaning at the levels of words, phrases, sentences, or larger units of discourse. One of the crucial questions which unites different approaches to linguistic semantics is that of the relationship between form and meaning. Semantics involves the deconstruction of words, signals, and sentence structure. It influences our reading comprehension as well as our comprehension of other people's words in everyday conversation. Semantics play a large part in our daily communication, understanding and language learning without us even realizing it. For example, in everyday use, a child might make use of semantics to understand a mom's directive to "do your chores" as, "do your chores whenever you feel like it." However, the mother was probably saying, "do your chores right now."(4)

Definition of Meaning

Semantics is the study of meaning, but what do we mean by „meaning“? Meaning has been given different definitions in the past. Meaning equals connotation. The meaning is simply the set of associations that a word evokes, and it is the meaning of a word defined by the images that its users connect to it. So „winter“ might mean „snow“, „sledging“ and „mulled wine“. But what about someone living in the amazon? Their „winter“ is still wet and hot, so its original

meaning is lost. Because the associations of a word don't always apply, it was decided that this couldn't be the whole story.(4)

Sense Relations

Here are a few of the ways in which words can be semantically related:

1. Synonymy – Words are synonymous/ synonyms when they can be used to mean the same thing (at least in some contexts – words are rarely fully identical in all contexts). Begin and start, Big and large, Youth and adolescent.

2. Antonymy Words are antonyms of one another when they have opposite meanings (again, at least in some contexts). Big and small, Come and gsemantic, Up and down.

3. Polysemy – A word is polysemous when it has two or more related meanings. In this case the word takes one form but can be used to mean two different things. In the case of polysemy, these two meanings must be related in some way, and not be two completely unrelated meanings of the word. Bright (shining) and bright (intelligent). Mouse (animal) and mouse (computer hardware).

4. Homophony – Homophony is similar to polysemy in that it refers to a single form of word with two meanings, however a word is a homophone when the two meanings are entirely unrelated. Bat (flying mammal) and bat (sports equipment). Pen (writing instrument) and pen (small cage).(4)

Theories in linguistic Semantics

Formal semantics

Formal semantics seeks to identify domain-specific mental operations which speakers perform when they compute a sentence's meaning on the basis of its syntactic structure. Theories of formal semantics are typically floated on top of theories of syntax such as generative syntax or

Combinatory categorial grammar and provide a model theory based on mathematical tools such as typed lambda calculi. The field's central ideas are rooted in early twentieth century philosophical logic as well as later ideas about linguistic syntax. It emerged as its own subfield in the 1970s after the pioneering work of Richard Montague and Barbara Partee and continues to be an active area of research. Formal semantics uses techniques from math, philosophy, and logic to analyze the broader relationship between language and reality, truth and possibility.(4)

Types of Semantics

Conceptual semantics

This theory is an effort to explain properties of argument structure. The assumption behind this theory is that syntactic properties of phrases reflect the meanings of the words that head them. With this theory, linguists can better deal with the fact that subtle differences in word meaning correlate with other differences in the syntactic structure that a word appears in. The way this is gone about is by looking at the internal structure of words. These small parts that make up the internal structure of words are termed semantic primitives.(4)

Cognitive semantics

Cognitive semantics approaches meaning from the perspective of cognitive linguistics. In this framework, language is explained via general human cognitive abilities rather than a domain-specific language module.

The techniques native to cognitive semantics are typically used in lexical studies such as those put forth by Leonard Talmy, George Lakoff, Dirk Geeraerts, and Bruce Wayne Hawkins. Some cognitive semantic frameworks, such as that developed by Talmy, take into account syntactic structures as well. Semantics, through modern researchers can be linked to the Wernicke's area of the brain and can be measured using the event-related potential (ERP). ERP is the rapid electrical response recorded with small disc electrodes which are placed on a person's scalp.(4)

Lexical semantics

A linguistic theory that investigates word meaning. This theory understands that the meaning of a word is fully reflected by its context. Here, the meaning of a word is constituted by its contextual relations. Therefore, a distinction between degrees of participation as well as modes of participation are made. In order to accomplish this distinction any part of a sentence that bears a meaning and combines with the meanings of other constituents is labeled as a semantic constituent. Semantic constituents that cannot be broken down into more elementary constituents are labeled minimal semantic constituents.(4)

Semantic Memory

In psychology, semantic memory is memory for meaning – in other words, the aspect of memory that preserves only the gist, the general significance, of remembered experience – while episodic memory is memory for the ephemeral details – the individual features, or the unique particulars of experience. The term 'episodic memory' was introduced by Tulving and Schacter in the context of 'declarative memory' which involved simple association of factual or objective information concerning its object. Word meaning is measured by the company they keep, the

relationships among words themselves in a semantic network. The memories may be transferred intergenerationally or isolated in one generation due to a cultural disruption.(4)

Conclusion

In language, syntax and semantics are closely related. Syntax provides the structure of sentences, while semantics gives them meaning. Neither works alone – both must interact for communication to be clear and effective.

Research shows that this connection is important in language learning and sentence processing. Learning how syntax and semantics work together can help improve areas such as translation, speech recognition, and language teaching.

In short, language is not only about structure or meaning, but also about the combination of the two. A deeper understanding of their connection leads to a better understanding of human connection.

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